

Fabrication, Structural and Electrochemical Characterization of Few Cathode Epitaxial Thin Films For All Solid Thin Film Batteries

K. Kamala Bharathi

Department of Physics, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, India

Email: kamalabharathi.k@ktr.srmuniv.ac.in

Abstract:

Evolution of technology in the field of energy storage has a great leap in past three decades with the help of Li ion batteries (LIB's).¹ However, all-solid-state thin film batteries are significantly less established, and have not yet been bump into commercial success. Engineering the materials behind all-solid-state systems has succeeded thus far-producing several electrolyte and cathode candidates.² In the present case, Fabrication and characterization of high quality, highly oriented epitaxial, high stable, high capacity and high voltage cathode thin film Li_2MnO_3 , $\text{LiCo}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$ and LiCoO_2 with a high density will be discussed and presented. Cathode thin films grown on SrTiO_3 (STO) (100), (110) and (111) oriented substrates exhibit (104), (110) and (001) orientations respectively. SrRuO_3 (SRO) epitaxial oxide layer was employed as a bottom electrode for measuring electrochemical properties of cathode films. All the cathode films exhibit high and stable capacity. Detailed structure-electrochemical property correlation will be discussed in the presentation.

Keywords:

All-Solid Battery, LiCoO_2 , Epitaxial Film, Electrochemical Properties.

Figure 1: (a) Cross-sectional TEM image of LiCoO_2 Thin film grown on SRO/STO (111), indicating the layered structure of the film. (b) SEM images indicating the surface morphology of LiCoO_2 thin films grown at different temperatures and different substrates.

References:

1. Goodenough, J. B., Kim, Y. (2010), Challenges for Rechargeable Li Batter-ies, *Chem. Mater.* 22, 587-603.
2. Takeuchi, S., Tan, H., Kamala Bhara-thi, K., Stafford, G. R., Shin, J., Yasui, S., Takeuchi, I., Bendersky, L. A. (2015), Epitaxial LiCoO₂ Films as a Model System for Fundamental Elec-trochemical Studies of Positive Elec-trodes. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 7, 7901–7911.